

Transformations of β -Pinene over Platinum-Alumina Catalyst Part—I: Influence of Contact Time, Temperature and Platinum Concentration

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Manuscript received 27 April 1981, revised 9 November 1981, accepted 23 May 1982

The catalytic transformations of β -pinene have been investigated over platinum-alumina dual function catalyst containing varying amounts of platinum in the temperature range 200 to 400°. In addition, the influence of contact time on the rate and distribution of products has been studied over 0.6% platinum-alumina at 300°. The performance of the catalyst remains unchanged by its pretreatment either in hydrogen or in oxygen prior to catalytic run. The dehydrogenation activity of the catalyst increases upto 350° beyond which it declines

β -Pinene isomerizes via two parallel paths, one giving rise to bi- and tricyclic products such as camphene, α -pinene, bornylene and tricyclene and the other giving monocyclic compounds such as dipentene, terpinolene, α - and γ -terpinenes. The terpinenes have been identified as the immediate precursors of cymene. Apart from this, the terpinenes undergo disproportionation to menthenes and menthanes. At higher values of contact time and temperature, menthenes and menthanes get dehydrogenated to cymenes.

Increase of platinum concentration inhibits both isomerization and dehydrogenation activities of the catalyst. This decrease is ascribed to reduction of the acid sites and enhancement of platinum crystallite size. Disproportionation reaction is favoured by strong acid sites and small well dispersed platinum crystallites.

β -Pinene is a bicyclic mono-olefinic monoterpene present together with α -pinene in the majority of essential oils derived from coniferae¹. The first quality Indian turpentine oil contains about 10% β -pinene, 40% α -pinene and 50% 3-carene². These hydrocarbons undergo skeletal isomerization initially due to the cleavage of cyclobutane and cyclopropane rings followed by dehydrogenation and disproportionation reactions over dual function catalysts such as chromia and chromia-alumina catalysts³⁻⁵.

Platinum-alumina, another important bifunctional catalyst, is being increasingly employed in reforming processes as it is found to have enhanced sustained activity and high selectivity. Hence platinum-alumina catalyst was chosen for this work. Further, a survey of literature reveals that a systematic investigation of the transformation of β -pinene over this catalyst in the vapour phase has not so far been reported. The influence of contact time, platinum concentration and temperature on the rate and distribution of products of β -pinene was therefore studied and the results are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Preparation of catalysts:

Alumina (catalyst A): Alumina was prepared according to the method of Pines *et al.*⁶

Platinum-alumina (catalysts B, C, D and E)
The catalysts B, C, D and E were prepared by adding calculated volumes of chloroplatinic acid in water to four weighed samples of alumina to give respectively 0.3, 0.6, 0.9 and 1.4% platinum by weight (confirmed by spectrophotometric analysis⁷). The slurry was stirred for 3 hr and dried at 120° for 24 hr. The temperature was raised slowly while passing pure dry hydrogen to reach 500° in a period of 2 hr and maintained at this for 8 hr. The activated material was powdered and pelletized to 4 x 4 mm size pellets.

TABLE 1—NOMENCLATURE OF THE CATALYST

Catalyst	Composition
A	Alumina (from aluminium isopropoxide)
B	Platinum-alumina (0.3% Pt)
C	Platinum-alumina (0.6% Pt)
D	Platinum-alumina (0.9% Pt)
E	Platinum-alumina (1.4% Pt)

β -Pinene: Since β -pinene (b.p. 165°) constitutes only 10% of first quality Indian turpentine oil and also it boils very close to 3-carene (b.p. 169°), the separation of this component by fractional distillation was not successful. Hence it was obtained from "Fluka" and its purity was checked by gas chromatography.

Apparatus and procedure: Initial experiments conducted both over oxidised and reduced catalysts did not show any significant variation in the product distribution as indicated in Table 3. Subsequent runs were, therefore, conducted over oxidised catalyst. Other details of the apparatus and experimental procedure have been described in the earlier publications⁸⁻¹⁰. The evolution of molecular hydrogen during this investigation was small due to side reactions. Hence the gaseous products were not considered for computing the *p*-cymene yield.

Surface area: The surface area measurements of catalysts C, D and E were made according to BET method, by adsorption of nitrogen at liquid nitrogen temperature. The experimental procedure and calculations were the same as described by Emmett¹¹. The values are found to be 121.1, 171.7 and 230.7 m²/g respectively. The platinum metal area for the above three catalysts are found to be 30.5, 48.4 and 58.5 m²/g of catalyst respectively by carbon monoxide adsorption, according to procedure described by Dorling¹².

Results and Discussion

(a) **Contact time:** In order to determine the transformation sequence of β -pinene, the influence of contact time W/F (where W is the weight of catalyst and F is the weight of β -pinene passed per hr over the catalyst) on the product distribution has been studied at 300° over catalyst C (0.6% Pt) and the results are plotted in Fig. 1, while the overall conversion is summarised in Table 2. The

Fig. 1. Effect of contact time on product distribution.

distribution of products varied to different extents with increasing contact time (Fig. 1). The various compounds formed are identified to be α -pinene, dipentene, terpinolene, α - and γ -terpinenes, camphene, tricyclene, bornylene, 1-, 3- and 4(8)-*p*-menthenes, *cis*- and *trans*-menthanes and *p*-cymene.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CONTACT TIME, PLATINUM CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURE ON THE OVERALL CONVERSION OF β -PINENE

Contact Time (hr)	% conversion of β -pinene	% platinum concentration	% conversion of β -pinene	Temperature (°C)	% conversion of β -pinene
0.12	84.0	0.3	98.7	250	98.3
0.4	92.0	0.6	98.8	300	98.8
0.79	98.8	0.9	98.9	350	98.8
1.2	99.0	1.4	98.6	400	97.8
1.6	99.5				

The concentration of individual menthadienes, menthenes and menthanes were too small and varied widely with contact time; hence they were grouped as menthadienes, menthenes and menthanes. The concentration of *p*-cymene continues to increase with increase in contact time. It can be inferred from this that *p*-cymene is the final product in the transformation of β -pinene and the rest are only intermediates, though formed through different routes (Scheme) and exhibit their maxima at different contact times. Further, it has been observed experimentally that *p*-cymene undergoes neither side chain dehydrogenation nor ring hydrogenation under the experimental conditions. This lends support to the above view regarding the nature of *p*-cymene.

Bornylene and tricyclene register an increase upto 1.2 hr; thereafter their concentrations remain almost constant. This may be due to the establishment of dynamic equilibrium among tricyclene, bornylene and camphene. Camphene formed by the skeletal isomerization of α - and β -pinenes suffers further skeletal isomerization to monocyclic menthadienes at higher contact time and at higher temperature.

The concentrations of α - and γ -terpinenes were less than the concentrations of dipentene and terpinolene at all contact times studied (Fig. 2). The reason for the low concentration of terpinenes could be the faster rate with which they undergo dehydrogenation as soon as they are formed from dipentene and terpinolene. This observation reveals that terpinenes are the immediate precursors of *p*-cymene.

Menthanes also undergo dehydrogenation like menthadienes but this occurs at higher contact time. Thus the maxima for menthadienes and menthanes occur around 0.12 and 0.79 hr respectively. On the basis of their dehydrogenation to cymenes, menthanes cannot be designated as intermediates like menthadienes since they are formed by disproportionation of menthadienes

SCHEME

Fig. 2. Effect of contact time on the percentage composition of menthadienes.

which is only a side reaction, not forming part of the dehydrogenation sequence of β -pinene :

However, they can be described as 'pseudo intermediates' which seems to be precise nomenclature on account of their increasing concentration to a maximum followed by a decrease.

Menthenes can either be formed by partial hydrogenation of menthadienes or by partial dehy-

drogenation of menthanes or by disproportionation of menthadienes. The first possibility is highly unlikely under this condition. Pines *et al.*¹⁸ reported that dehydrogenation of menthanes to cymenes over platinum-alumina occurred without the intermediate formation of menthenes and menthadienes. Menthenes are therefore considered to be the disproportionation products of menthadienes as shown below :

From these observations, the sequence of reactions pertaining to the formation of various products from β -pinene is shown in the Scheme.

(b) *Platinum concentration* : In Table 2 and in Fig. 3 are given the influence of platinum concentrations on the overall conversion of β -pinene and the distribution of products respectively at 300° and at a contact time of 0.79 hr. There is no variation in the overall conversion of β -pinene with increasing platinum concentration as it has reacted almost completely even at 0.3% platinum concentration, showing that β -pinene is highly reactive. On the other hand the various species present in the catalysate are influenced to varying degrees by increased platinum additions. For instance, the proportions of α -pinene and camphene increase while those of tricyclene and menthene decrease. *p*-Cymene and menthanes, after registering their maxima over 0.9% and 0.6% platinum respectively, begin to fall. Bornylene increases to a maximum, whereas menthadienes decrease to a minimum, thereafter the former and the latter register decreasing and increasing trends respectively (Fig. 3).

α -Pinene and camphene, formed initially from β -pinene, may not be able to undergo further

Fig. 3. Effect of platinum concentration on product distribution.

skeletal isomerization due to decrease of the acidic sites of alumina by deposition of platinum metal and hence their concentration in the catalysate increases. Consequently the concentrations of tricyclene, bornylene, menthenes and menthanes in the catalysate decrease.

Among the transition metals, platinum, being the most effective dehydrogenating element, is expected to show greater activity for dehydrogenation reaction when its content in the catalyst increases. But actually a decrease in its activity is observed. Platinum metal area of catalysts C, D and E are 30.5, 48.4 and 58.5 m²/g of catalyst (and not per gram of platinum). Though the surface area registers an increasing trend, the rate of increase registers a fall in magnitude with increasing platinum concentrations. This is possibly due to a

tendency of the platinum crystallites to form clusters at higher concentration. This is reflected by corresponding decrease in the dehydrogenation activity and the increase in concentration of menthadienes. The decrease in the menthane concentration indicates that disproportionation reactions are favoured by both strong acid sites and small well-dispersed metal crystallites. Since at higher platinum concentrations these types of essential sites namely strong acid sites and well dispersed metal sites disappear, a decrease in the concentration of menthanes occurs.

(c) *Temperature*: The effect of temperature on the total conversion of β -pinene and on the distribution of products has been studied over catalyst C at 0.79 hr and the results are presented in Table 2 and Fig. 4, respectively. The catalyst has developed its maximum activity even at 250° with regard to the overall conversion of β -pinene. Temperature beyond 350° has no beneficial effect.

Fig. 4. Effect of temperature on product distribution.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF CATALYST PRETREATMENT ON THE PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION: D^a=0.9% Pt-Al₂O₃, REDUCED; D^b=0.9% Pt-Al₂O₃, NOT REDUCED AFTER REGENERATION; E^a=1.4% Pt-Al₂O₃, REDUCED AFTER REGENERATION; E^b=1.4% Pt-Al₂O₃, NOT REDUCED AFTER REGENERATION

Sl. No.	Temp. °C	Contact time (hr)	Catalyst	β -Pinene reacted	α -Pinene	Camphene	Menthadienes	Cymene	Tricyclene	Bornylene	Menthene	Menthane	Carbon estimated
1	250	0.79	D ^a	98.8	24.6	19.0	1.6	34.7	5.0	3.3	5.0	6.8	0.56
2			D ^b	98.8	20.4	21.5	4.8	34.6	5.0	3.5	4.0	6.2	0.6
1	350	0.79	E ^a	98.2	12.8	19.4	2.2	58.7	3.0	2.8	3.0	3.1	0.5
2			E ^b	98.7	18.9	20.1	3.2	54.8	3.0	1.8	2.2	2.0	0.6

a = reduced after regeneration.
b = not reduced after regeneration.

In fact a small deactivation of the catalyst was noted around 400°. Temperature around 400° may promote undesired side reactions like cracking and polymerization, leading to the formation of coke which may cause the deactivation of the catalyst.

The proportions of various intermediates, irrespective of their nature, fall rapidly due to their further conversion to the final product, *p*-cymene, which maintains its increasing trend almost linearly upto 350°. Between 350 and 400°, the *p*-cymene formation comes down on account of the deactivation of the catalyst as explained above.

The maximum concentration of menthanes and menthenes occurs around 250° and thereafter their formation registers a decrease. From this it is clear that disproportionation reactions are favoured in the lower temperature regions since at higher temperature the species undergoing disproportionation desorb easily before reaction.

Acknowledgement

Thanks of the authors are due to Dr. G. S. Laddha, Director, A. C. College of Technology, Madras, for necessary facilities.

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